

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE MAIN FEATURES OF PHONOTACTICS IN THE AZERBAIJANI AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The article has been written on the bases of comparative-tyological method in the study of the English and Azerbaijani languages belonging to different language systems (English belonging to analytical type of languages, Azerbaijani to the synthetic type of languages. The main aim of the investigation is to find out similarities and differentiations between phonotactics in the English and Azerbaijani languages.

Keywords: phonotactics, monophthong, diphthong, consonant, excursion phase, recursion stage.

Introduction. The etymology of the word “phonotactics” comes from the Greek word “phone”, “sound” and “taktike” “the art of placement”. Speaking of phonotactics, we mean a combination of phonemes in different positions in a word and a morpheme. Phonotactic restrictions investigate all possible sequences of phonemes in a language. A syllable is a phonotactic unit. The rules that form the basis of the syllable structure that exists in each language, and the rules regulating them, are called phonotactic restrictions.

In English, there are phonotactic rules that reveal which combinations of phonemes are permissible or not permissible at the junction of syllables. Despite the fact that, in the initial position, the combination of such consonants as (sk, st, sp) is often used, but combinations of the same phonemes, in the combinations (ps, pt, ks) are not used in the initial position in English words. Speaking about the phonotactic possibilities of the English language, the following features can be noted: long monophthongs and diphthongs in the English language cannot precede the consonant sound /ŋ/; nasal sonant /ŋ/ is not used in the initial position; it is not possible to combine such phonemes as /tʃ, dʒ, ð, z/ with consonants in the initial position; phonemes /r, j, w/ cannot act as the first element in combinations with consonants; vowel phonemes such as /e, æ, ʌ, ɒ/ are not found in the final position. Phoneme /r/ is characterized by rotacism, the absence of rotacism, the use of intrusive and linking /r/. In the words with the letter “r, the rotic /r/ is used. This phenomenon occurs in American English. The absence of rotacism occurs in British English. If the word ends with the letter “r”, and the following word begins with a vowel, in this case linking /r/ is used. For example: His father and mother are engineers. Intrusive /r/ is used even if the word ends in a vowel, and the following word begins with a vowel. For example: The idea of Africa and Asia. The combination of such phonemes as /fs, mh, stl, spw/ in the initial position is unknown. Consonant phonemes such as /h, j, r, w/ are not found in the final position in the English language. If in the final position such sonants as /m, n/ do not form a syllable, then in this case the sonorous sound /l/ may precede them. In the final position, the combination of phonemes such as /kf, ʃp, lð, ʒbd/ is unknown. The combination of consonant phonemes like [tw, dw, gw] before vowels can be used

at the beginning of a word; the twomembered combination of the consonant [sp] in the initial position may occur before all vowels; from the twelve possible three-membered combinations of consonants, nine of them can be used in English, but such threemembered combinations as [spw-, stl-, stw-] in the final position are not used. [5, c 243].

2. Scope of the study

Words in a language have a certain phonetic composition, structure. There is no word in the language that has no phonetic content: each word combines at least three aspects - a sound complex, a meaning, and a source of meaning. To be a language unit of any sound complex, the combination of sounds in each language must be organized in accordance with certain phonetic laws, phonetic rules. For example, in English, if there are three consonants at the beginning of the word, such combinations of consonants in the Azerbaijani language are not allowed. On the other hand, the words cannot begin with the combination of consonants [tn, tl], but these combinations can be used in the final position of the words in English. In the Türkic languages, vowels in the composition of the word have the same features. In the composition of one word, it is possible to combine either front vowels or back vowels.

In English, not all consonants at the beginning of the word can be combined with each other. In this position we can show the two-structured form of the twomembered combination of consonants. For example, 1) Spirant + consonant (S + C). For example, stay [s t e i], swim [s w i m], sleep [s l i: p]. 2) Consonant + [w, r, l, j]: twin [t w I n], cream [k r i: m], plain [p l e i n], beauty [b j u: t i] [5, p.243]. From the two modular structures, it can be concluded that the occlusive plosives, in combination constrictive sonorants in the initial position can form a two-membered combination. Such a structure as a spirant + occlusive is in the second place. However, two-membered combinations such as [sr, sb, sb, tl, hr, fw] are beyond the limit of the types of noted structures. On the other hand, it is possible to determine three types of structure of a twomembered combination in anlaut. On the other hand, at the beginning of a word, three types of twomembered consonant combinations can be defined: 1) occlusive plosives + sonorant, 2) fricative + sonorant, 3) fricative + fortis (voiceless) stop (Gimson, 1970).

In the final position of the twomembered combination, five models can be distinguished: 1) consonant + / t, d, s, z / For example, begged, since, act, helped. 2) sonorant + consonant For example, help, sold. 3) / m, n / + consonant For example, ink, lung. 4) consonant + interdental / θ / For example, fifths, length. 5) / r / + consonant For example, work, birth. According to A. Jimson, such consonants as [r, h, j, w] in English in the final position cannot form combinations with other consonants; consonants such as [g, ŋ, ð] in twomembered consonant combinations cannot act as the last element; the combination [pθ] only with [e], the combination [mθ] only with [ɔ:], the combination [ln] only with [e], [fθ] with [i] can be used after all vowels; only the combination [dz] can be used after all vowels; vowels such as [ɪ, e, ʌ] have a greater tendency in the formation of a combination of vowels with consonants. In English, all consonants can be found in the initial position in the words. This combination is found in proper nouns of foreign origin. For example, Ngami / ŋa: mɪ / (Gimson, 1970).

3. Research Methodology

In the article we have used comparative typological method in the investigation of the main features of phonotactics in the Azerbaijani and English languages

4. The main features of phonotactics in the Azerbaijani and English languages

According to the phonotactics of the Azerbaijani language, two vowels or two consonants cannot be combined at the beginning of a word. In addition, there are several sound combinations, such as [ggcaa], [ioac], [mnfra] and so on. Typical sound combinations can never be a part of the phonetic structure in Azerbaijani words (Axundov, 1973). Therefore, the sound content of each language is formed on the basis of specific phonetic laws and rules, and function in a language. Regarding to the distribution of vowels in the structure of the word in the Azerbaijani language, A. Akhundov notes the followings: 1) The most typical position for Azerbaijani vowels is the middle position. 2) The combination of two vowels at the beginning of a word and five vowels at the end of a word is not used. Vowels such as [e, ö, o] are not typical for the final position. For the final position, six vowels are typical such as [i, ü, ə, ɪ, u, a]. 3) In the Azerbaijani language, regardless of the phonetic and morphological position, the most common are non-labialized, open vowels such as [ə] and [a]. 4) The most widely used long vowels in the Azerbaijani language are [i:] and [a:]. 5) The frequency of use in the Azerbaijani language is indicated as follows: [a, a, i, i, u, u, u, e, ö; a:, i:, e:, o:] (Axundov, 1984). There are certain limitations in the development of vowel phonemes in combinations of VC and CV in the Azerbaijani language. A. Akhundov's research shows that all vowel phonemes cannot be used before all consonants. It is revealed that when vowel sound [ö:] is used less before consonants, and the most commonly used vowel sounds are [i:], [u:], [a:]. As in the case of VC, there are some limitations in the combination of vowel phonemes after various consonants (CV). In this type of combination, a vowel phoneme such as [ö:] is less used after various consonants (Axundov, 1984).

In the Azerbaijani language, there is a serious limitation in the combination of vowels if they are joined. All vowel sounds cannot be used at the junction of words. Akhundov's research shows that there are two strict phonetic rules in the development of various variants of the Azerbaijani language. The first of them is manifested in short variations of closed vowels, and the second - in a slightly decreasing labialization of the lips. Closed vowels in the Azerbaijani language are reduced in different phonetic positions. If the number of syllables increases, then in this case closed vowels that stand before unstressed syllables are reduced. Thus, the closed syllable is reduced: 1) words consisting of two syllables on the first unstressed syllable; 2) words consisting of three syllables on the second unstressed syllable; 3) in four-syllable words on the third unstressed syllable; 4) and in the words of five syllables on the fourth unstressed syllable. For example, sinif, sinfi, sinfimizin; bulud, buludun, buludunuz. But in monosyllabic words, closed vowels are not reduced. For example, biz, gül, qız, quş (Axundov, 1984). Speaking about the physical-acoustic features of phonetic components, their phases, A. Akhundov shows the following common features for the consonants of the Azerbaijani language: 1) the excursion phase for all voiced consonants at the beginning of the word leads to devoicing; 2) the recursion stage of all consonants at the end of a word leads to devoicing; 3) the excursion phase of all voiceless consonants after vowels leads to a slight voicing; 4) all consonant phonemes are labialized depending on the phonetic position in which they fall; (Axundov, 1984). In Azeri, occlusive plosive voiceless consonants such as [p, t, k, k̥] in all positions of the structure of the word may have such a characteristic feature as aspiration. Aspiration in the Azerbaijani language is most characteristic for the final position. All aspirated consonants lose aspiration after consonant [s]. At the same time, A. Akhundov notes that at the end of complex words, voiced consonants are aspirated in some cases (Axundov, 1984).

The distributional features of the consonants of the Azerbaijani language can be summarized as follows: 1) Like the vowels, the most typical position for consonants is the middle position. In the Azerbaijani language, at the beginning of the word, the phoneme [g̃] is not used. At the end of the word noisy consonants are used more than sonorous consonants. In the initial and middle positions, lingual, occlusive, voiced, noisy and oral consonants are used more frequently. The same consonants are characteristic for the initial position (Axundov, 1984). Fricative, voiceless and oral consonants are more often used in the root of the word than in the suffixes in the Azerbaijani language. As a rule, lingual, occlusive, voiced, noisy, oral consonants are more characteristic for the root of a word. Sonorous consonants are more characteristic of suffixes. Consonants in frequency of use in the Azerbaijani language are listed as follows: [l, n, r, m, d, y, s, b, t, k, z, g, g, k, x, h, v, c, k, f, n, j] (Axundov, 1984). Regarding the ability to connect consonants with vowels and consonants in the Azerbaijani language, the following can be mentioned: 1) Only [b] cannot be combined with another consonant in the Azerbaijani language. If we take

into consideration [m, d, r] and [n], all consonants can be used at the junction of words, but [l] can be used together with [j] on the border with the morpheme. [d] can be used with such consonants as [p, f, t, ç, k, g, x] (Axundov, 1988). There are no restrictions on the consonants of the Azerbaijani language before the vowels. Only consonants [v, j, k, g] and [ğ] cannot be used before all vowels in a given language. Thus, [v] is not used before [ö], and [k] is not used before [ı], [j], [g] and [ğ] before the four consonants [3, p. 145]. According to F. Jalilov, the modern [ŋ] phoneme in modern Azerbaijani language is not functioning any longer, and the allophone [ũ] which is formed from the phoneme [y] and [k] is more activated. Thus, in such words as [inəũ, çörəũ] or [inəx, çörəx], a deaf allophone of the [y] phoneme is used. This allophone we indicate in transcription as follows, as [ũ] or [x]. In the Azerbaijani language, the allophone of the constrictive consonant [k] is noted as [ũ]. For example, məktəb, məktub [məũtəp, məũtup] [4, p. 64-65].

Speaking about the connections of consonants in the initial and final positions in the Azerbaijani language, F. Jalilov notes that two vowels, two consonants are not used, in this position the phonemes like [r], [j] do not occur, the consonants [l], [m], [n], [z], [v] are less found in the above position, and delving into the ancient era, we reveal that they were not used in this position. In the middle and final position, two vowels are not found. In the Azerbaijani language, if two consonants are found in the final position, then one of them is usually a sonorous sound. There are some differences between phonotactics of words and suffixes in the Azerbaijani language. Thus, such consonants as [l, n, r, ŋ] are not found in the initial position of the word, but most of the morphemes begin with the given phonemes. On the other hand, all vowels are used in the root of the word, but in suffixes vowel phonemes such as [e, o, ɔ] are not found. As F. Jalilov notes that, the combination of two or three consonants in the Azerbaijani language

from the point of view of the diachronic aspect is a subsequent phenomenon, because such combinations of qır-x-qır, kök-üs-kök, gör-üklü-gör-üklü appeared in the morphological connection (Cəlilov, 1988).

F. Veyselli notes that the Azerbaijani language is a language that adheres to the rules of VC or CV. The subtlety of the Azerbaijani language is that in the nest of one vowel several vowel sounds cannot be combined. Further he writes: "The second feature that distinguishes our language from other languages is that the characteristic feature of our words is that they are always at their peak. In Azerbaijani, the first root vowel is characterized by the fact that the subsequent vowel in the suffix acquires the same feature. For example, if words begin with front-vowels, then the front-vowel is also used in suffixes or vice versa, for example, ata-lardan, iki-miz-in.

Conclusion. Comparative -typological analysis of the materials of the English and Azerbaijani languages helps us to come to the following conclusions. Studies show that English and Azerbaijani languages have their own phonotactic features.

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